

Enhanced External Counterpulsation in Refractory Angina: A Systematic Review with Potential Relevance for Perioperative Risk Stratification

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Introduction

Patients presenting for cardiac or major non-cardiac surgery with refractory angina represent a high-risk population, often unsuitable for further revascularization and prone to perioperative ischemic complications. Enhanced External Counterpulsation (EECP) is a non-invasive therapy that has been shown to improve coronary perfusion and reduce anginal symptoms. While primarily used for symptom control, its role in preoperative optimization remains underexplored. This systematic review evaluates short-term effects of EECP on Canadian Cardiovascular Society (CCS) angina class and explores its relevance in high-risk surgical patients.

Materials and Methods

A systematic literature search of PubMed, EMBASE, and Scopus was conducted on 10 September 2025 using predefined terms related to EECP, refractory angina, and CCS angina class. Eligible studies included patients with refractory or non-revascularizable angina and reporting CCS class changes within one month post-treatment. Non-English publications, conference abstracts, reviews, and studies lacking post-intervention CCS assessment were excluded. Methodological quality was assessed using the NIH Quality Assessment Tool and ROBINS-I. Outcomes were summarized as proportions achieving "e1 and "e2 CCS class improvement. Due to heterogeneity of comparators, results were synthesized narratively.

Results

Thirteen studies comprising 2,213 patients were included; most were single-arm prospective studies of fair methodological quality. Across studies, 77–100% achieved "e1 CCS showed no change. Among studies reporting "e2-class improvement, 12–included studies evaluated perioperative or surgical populations; however, consistent symptomatic improvement suggests possible relevance in patients who may be considered for surgery.

Conclusion

EECP is associated with clinically meaningful short-term improvement in angina severity. Although direct perioperative evidence is lacking, reduction in symptom burden suggests a possible role in preoperative optimization for high-risk surgical candidates not eligible for further revascularization. These findings are hypothesis-generating and warrant prospective studies evaluating the impact of EECP on perioperative outcomes and surgical risk stratification.

Keywords

Enhanced External Counterpulsation (EECP); Refractory angina; Canadian Cardiovascular Society (CCS) class; Non-invasive therapy; Coronary perfusion; Preoperative optimization; Perioperative risk stratification